

TYPES OF ECOLOGICAL MANAGEMENT OF WATER RESOURCES AND LEVELS OF BIOINDICATION APPROACH

¹Mirzabekova Maftuna daughter of Abduljalil, ²Askarov Nodirbek son of Daniyor

¹UzMU, PhD student

²Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute, student

Annotation. *In the world, as a result of the increase in the need for water resources and its unreasonable use, anthropogenic and natural effects on water resources, there are structural changes, changes in the properties and ecological status of water and water resources, and an increase in pollution indices. This is the reason for the disruption of the prospects of achieving sustainable development in the conditions of current climate changes and the emergence of serious environmental and socio-economic problems on a global scale. At this point, the ecological analysis of changes in water resources and the study of influencing factors are of great scientific and practical importance.*

Key words: water, resource, ecology, hydrographic, hydroecology, hydrology, river, soil.

The concept of sustainable development of the use of water resources has been adopted, requiring an impartial assessment of the problems facing the world community today: including drinking water sources, reserves and factors affecting it negatively, the quality, quantity, mineralization of water resources used for irrigation, water. Special attention is being paid to the implementation of scientific research on soil salinity levels, changes in quantity and quality of collector-drainage water in arable lands[1;2].

Based on the environmental conditions of different regions, it is necessary to determine the conditions for sustainable use of water resources, to maximally implement national goals and tasks in the field of sustainable development.

In the address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis and the people of Uzbekistan, among the top priorities in 2023, "ecology, especially water issues are becoming a global problem, serious environmental problems are emerging in Uzbekistan as well as in the world. lack of water, drought, providing the population with clean drinking water, preserving our nature, keeping water, air and the environment clean, strengthening requirements for the protection of water bodies and underground reserves, transparent accounting of water the need to introduce a management system", Decree No. PF-5863 of October 31, 2019 "On approval of the concept of environmental protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" "... water and land important goals and tasks have been defined in terms of rational and economical use of resources, increasing soil fertility and agricultural crop productivity, further improving the reclamation condition of irrigated lands, production of ecologically clean products.

In the implementation of these goals and tasks, including the evaluation of the ecological aspects of the sustainable use of water resources of the Tashkent region, it acquires important scientific and practical importance. Tasks are clearly indicated in the Action Strategy for further economic and social development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. On the basis of these tasks, for example, the work on "Sustainable development" of our country; in particular, recommendations for taking measures to protect the environment, to further improve the ecological conditions of the atmosphere, hydrosphere, and lithosphere, and to apply new technological methods. The main purpose of these decrees and decisions is to fundamentally change the attitude to water resources, to permanently protect water resources, to prevent negative environmental consequences, and to

organize their efficient and rational use. The main purpose of these decrees and decisions is to fundamentally change the attitude to water resources, to permanently protect water resources, to prevent negative environmental consequences, and to organize their efficient and rational use.

Due to the fact that water resources, their quantity and quality aspects, ecological conditions are diverse in different regions, in their use, protection and agricultural production, the rational use of water resources should be taken into account the current climate change and the conditions of each region. and it should be aimed at protecting the environment [3;4].

Taking into account the above, the development and implementation of the ecological aspects of the sustainable use of water resources and the scientific basis of changes in the quantity and quality of water resources is one of the most urgent problems of today. This is of great scientific and practical importance. Especially in the implementation of the above-mentioned tasks, the importance of water in agriculture and social life, based on the current conditions, its reserve size, composition, quality, compliance with ecological requirements, and the study of its real purity in permanent laboratory conditions are of urgent importance. Annual water consumption in the world for all types of water supply is 3300-3500 km³. At the same time, 70% of all water consumption is used in agriculture.

The growth of cities, the rapid development of industry, the rapid development of agriculture, the significant expansion of irrigated land, the improvement of cultural and living conditions, and a number of other factors are increasingly complicating the problems of water supply. For example, it is important to determine the level of water pollution of rivers, canals, ditches, ditches passing through the city, its causes, and their prevention.

Ecological and hydrological aspects of water resources management. Theoretically and practically, all specialists in the field of water management are well aware of the dependence of all types of water resources on hydrological cycles within hydrographic basins based on the law of movement and balance of substances. But not all of them take this into account in their activities.

Water resources are formed, moved, returned and reused within hydrographic basins. All these processes are interrelated. Each hydrographic basin has its main riverbed, its reachable and non-reachable tributaries, dynamic groundwater reserves, and formed return water resources. The natural water content of the river depends on the precipitation falling into its basin and evaporation from this basin, the formation of flow modules, flows formed from glaciers and snow layers, and groundwater flows. The total balance of water resources in the basin consists of natural inflows and outflows of water and anthropogenic components of the flow returned to nature by humans. [6;7].

These organizers of the water balance are so diverse that it is difficult to list them, but they all exist and they affect the external ecological environments associated with them. We will try to systematize them:

In terms of change, result, consequence:

- increase (or decrease) of forests in the catchment area
- decrease (increase) of ground water level
- changes in the distribution of water volume and flow throughout the year;
- increase (or decrease) of erosion;
- agriculture in the zone of formation of water resources, including
- irrigated agriculture, increase in scale;
- increasing land productivity;
- increasing water turbidity;

- increase the flow of water to the lower horizons and located below the rise of the underground water level in the lands;
- increase in the extraction of surface water for irrigation and other purposes;
- reduction of water flow below water intake points;
- deterioration of water quality in the river;
- formation of return waters;
- increase in groundwater flow and change in their quality;
- change of soil quality.

However, all of the above-mentioned changes and effects can be regulated to a certain extent if clear criteria are developed and followed in the decision-making process of water resources management and use, based on the condition of hydro-ecological stability.

In this:

- exchange of water and salt between the river and the catchment area that saturates it should be minimized;
- the exchange of water and salt between the aeration zone and underground water should be zero;
- the amount of total water resources taken from the river should not exceed their limits that do not harm the natural requirements (river delta, wetlands, etc.).

Compliance with all these criteria, not only in years of average water, but also in years of low water and high water, requires the accuracy of data, predictions and models, as well as a strict procedure in the management and use of water resources in the basin and its separate parts. Unfortunately, in practice, even at the level of individual countries, there are cases of purposeful imbalances and changes in water supply. Parameters of natural and anthropogenic uncertainties cause a significant level of complexity in the hydrographic management of basins.

In practice, there are the following types of hydrographic uncertainty:

- oqimning tabiiy o‘zgaruvchanligi;
- mistakes made due to insufficient knowledge, inaccuracies in information or their lack;
- lack of models and the amount of errors in them;
- underdevelopment of the measurement system, errors in them, incorrect forms used in approximation (expressing mathematical quantities in the form of simpler quantities), etc.;
- Uncertainties in the decisions taken on the management of the river or its basin, which lead to changes in other sections of the river or basin, including changes in surface or underground water.

In the recent period, the level of information provision in the region has decreased slightly, even at the national level. The number of hydro-meteorological stations has decreased even on large rivers. There is very little information on water quality. Information exchange is insufficient not only between countries, but also within countries. All this leads to increasing uncertainties in management. As a result, it was not possible to predict the 2000 drought (low water level) in the region, and some areas of the Syrdarya and Amudarya basins were severely damaged[5;7].

In response to external influences, sustainable management of water resources should include an adaptive approach to management.

As integrated management of water resources is increasingly being adapted, the need for more active multi-sectoral cooperation, i.e. basin management and planning, is increasing. The future water supply in the world should take into account a number of destabilizing factors,

including population growth, economic growth, and waste pollution, as well as the possibility of water scarcity due to climate change. .

If we make a conclusion based on the statistical indicators that are updated day by day, we can see that alarming situations are emerging. However, the fact that all measures such as prevention and finding a solution are in our own hands, encourages us not to stop moving and searching. In order to further improve the attitude of the population to sewage and drinking water on the basis of the laws, decisions and decrees issued instead of the proposal, groups with the participation of representatives of special fields will be organized, control and clarification work will be made wider and more, and modern media will approach these problems more deeply. it is necessary to generate ideas.

LITERATURES

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. // Legislative Chamber of the Republic of Uzbekistan, September 14, 2015.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 6, 1993 No. 837-XII "On Water and Water Use", 1993. May 6, 837 - No. XII.
3. Decrees and decisions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers. 887-XII of March 6, 1996.
4. Decision No. 292 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On approval of the program for conducting state environmental monitoring in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2011-2015".
5. Isakova E.F., Kolosova L.V. Method biotestirovaniya s ispolzovaniem dafniy // Methody biotestirovaniya vody. Chernogolovka, 1988 S 50-55.
6. Kovalev V. It's alive. M.:, 2003.
7. Gudratov O., "Industrial ecology", Study guide, Tosh., 2005, 478 p.